

To: Parliament of The Republic of Ghana
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
From: A■■■■ K■■■■
CC: D. Owusu-Agyekum
Date: October 5th, 2021
Re: Written Memorandum on Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Introduction:

Following the United Nations definition of human rights below, “Human rights are rights inherent to all human beings, regardless of race, sex, nationality, ethnicity, language, religion, or any other status. Human rights include the right to life and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and education, and many more. Everyone is entitled to these rights, without discrimination” the proposed bill pursues a course of action which seeks to deny and violates the universally accepted definition of human rights for groups of people who identify as members and allies of the LGBTQI+ community in the Federal Republic of Ghana.

Supporting Argument:

Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by the United Nations, a body to which the Republic of Ghana belongs states that, “*all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and would act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood*”. Passing a bill to police the sexuality and consensual sexual expressions of citizens of the Republic takes away their sovereignty, dehumanizing them in ways that violates Article 5 “no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment” which has been proposed in this bill as conversion therapy.

The proposed bill claims “*LGBTQI+ activities threaten the concept of family and the associated value systems that are central to the social structure of all ethnic groups in Ghana.*” The word “activities” used in this claim implies a tangibility or action which is non-existent. If the word activity is prescribed to members of the LGBTQI+ community specifically has to do with sexual conducts, we can then umbrella the tern activity for sexual conducts of non LGBTQI+ members.

The bill also states, “*the concept of family for Ghanaians has always been of society-initiated marriage between a man and a woman whose genders are assigned at birth.*” It is not uncommon to have persons born intersex, conforming to either male or female. The bills claim of proper family virtues being marriage between female and male automatically ostracizes person who were born intersex. I argue that a person cannot be punished for the biological make up as that makes them unique. Whether or not this biological make up is considered an anomaly or a problem should be up to the persons with the make-up. No one has the right to determine what another person should look like.

Chapter 5 of the 1992 constitutions, particularly in articles 12(2) “Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this

Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.”

17(1) *All persons shall be equal before the law* and 21(1)(a) *freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media* and (d) *Freedom of assembly including freedom to take part in processions and demonstration, are laws the constitution accords every free citizen of the republic of Ghana.* Sections 21(1)(e) *Freedom of association which shall include freedom to form or join trade unions or other association, national and international, for the protection of their interest.*

By invading the LGBTQI+ community center, the government of Ghana violated Chapter 5, article 20(1). The parliament will argue 20(1)(a) in defense of this violation however, the safe space that was shut down had not hindered public safety, order, morality, health or town and country planning. Unless the state needed to accue the property for their own use under which the defense used to shut down the property illegally would have been fraudulent, and the LGBT Rights Ghana organization would have legal standing to sue the government of Ghana. If the bill is bold enough to mention that the constitution of the great republic of Ghana is not absolute, will the bill be calling the minds that put the documents together incapable or will this proposed bill be hinting towards a reformation or an amendment of the constitution of the Republic?

The bill mentions the need for a separation of prohibited acts from the right to engage in their advocacy. It goes further to state the prohibited acts are injurious to public health and safety thus any groups, organizations, or meetings to promote these prohibited acts will by extension be unlawful. Prohibited act here is defined as “unnatural carnal knowledge” within which the LGBTQI+ community were not listed. The phrase carnal knowledge is a rather archaic word for sexual intercourse and sexual intercourse is not limited to vaginal penetration with a penis. Sexual intercourse or in this case “carnal knowledge” is knowledge to be left for the consenting persons in its engagement.

I argue the reference to *Banosin v. The Republic*; No. J3/2/2014 dated 8th march 2014 has no grounding with this bill because it was a case of the rape of a minor.

“It is the female sex organs called the vulva and vagina that are normally penetrated into during any sexual act which can qualify to be carnal knowledge under sections 98 and 99 of Act 29”

The key word here is CAN. The statement did not definitively say the penetration of the vagina IS the absolute definition of carnal knowledge. The definition of sexual intercourse varies from person to person and while some form of penetration or insertion is needed for procreation, it would be quite backwards for the esteemed Republic of Ghana to assume that is the only function of sexual intercourse. The average Ghanaian family having less children than generations before is testament to the fact that sexual intercourse serves more than the need for procreation. It is a form of pleasure to be consensually enjoyed by adults.

The bill states that according to the 4th National HIV and AIDS Research Conference in Accra, 18.1% of people living with AIDS are gay men. That leaves 81.9% of people in Ghana living with AIDS who are NOT gay men. I believe astute attention to proper sex education with our youth which is not rooted in shame and guilt of natural biological changes which make them more susceptible to sexual explorations, as well as provision of support to at risk persons who utilize sex work as a means of survival might be a better way to combat AIDS.

Article 39, Clauses (1) and (2)

1) Subject to clause (2) of this article, the State shall take steps to encourage the integration of appropriate customary values into the fabric of national life through formal and informal education and the conscious introduction of cultural dimensions to relevant aspects of national, planning.

2) The State shall ensure that appropriate customary and cultural values are adapted and developed as an integral part of the growing needs of the society as a whole; and in particular that traditional practices which are injurious to the health and well-being of the person are abolished.

The bill assumes the above clauses lend themselves to marriage between male and female, automatically “othering” intersex individuals. This bill claims it seeks to strengthen the laws of the republic instead the enactment of this bill will create a separation, animosity, and division between the citizens of the republic. Ghana has earned a reputation for its maintenance of peace since acquiring independence, there is no telling what a bill of this stature could do to this peaceful foundation all Ghanaians have contributed to.

The bill itself states that there is NO LEGISLATION that specifically criminalized advocacy for, funding of, promotion of or encouragement of LGBTQI+ activities except the “*preparation for committing certain criminal offences, abetment of a criminal offence and conspiracy. The bill assumes a gap in the law creates opportunities for advocates of the LGBTQI+ community to sponsor, promote or proliferate “those” sexual activities* but it does not define what sexual activities those are, rendering that argument baseless. The bill mentions promised travel opportunities, allowances, and other gifts as incentives for persons to engage in LGBTQI+ activities (which again it does not clarify). Providing incentives in exchange for sexual favours hold no discrimination towards any sexual orientations. Thus, CONSENSUAL sexual engagements between adults IS not illegal. The degree to which two consenting adults choose to express themselves sexually cannot, by law, be policed by the state especially if those consenting adults are not reporting any harm experienced.

The bill argues its alignment with the United Nations SDG’s 3, 5 and 10. SDG 3 which is to “*ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages*” has no bearing with consensual sexual interactions of the people of the republic. If the parliament seeks to promote this SDG especially around sexual health and awareness, it could work on implementing a more robust sexual education, awareness, and resource centers to educate the republic and reduce the stigma around sex, sexuality, and sexual health overall. SDG 5 which is “*to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls*”, has nothing to do with this bill. Women and girls have been historically underrepresented, sidelined, silenced and their contributions have been unrecognized. Thus, this SDG is in place to prioritize the avenues and resources that will provide visibility to our women and girls to enable them to thrive within structures that have historically been patriarchal. SDG 10 which is to “*reduce inequality within and among countries*” puts the bill in a chokehold because its very nature propagates the very inequalities the SDG seeks to reduce.

There are many things that are humanely, ethically, and morally questionable with this proposed bill, however, below are consequences of the proposed bill according to some its clauses:

1. Clause 1 & 2 applies to persons who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, queer (which is an all-encompassing term), an ally (which extends to heterosexuals as well), pansexual or any other person of contrary “sociocultural” notions of male and female or the relationship between male and female relationship, a person born intersex, persons who support the LGBTQI+ community (who will be termed as an ally) and even some medical practitioners. The arm of this statement extends beyond a scope any citizen of the Republic of Ghana could comprehend and shadows over all citizens of the Republic of Ghana.
2. Clause 4 prohibits a person from engaging in acts that undermine the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values provided for in the bill. Carnal knowledge or sexual intercourse is an act that occurs within the privacy of consenting adults thus a ban or measure of what is natural or unnatural between consenting human adults seems rather peculiar. In easy words, this bill proposes to rid the Ghanaian adults from pleasures accrued from sexual activities like oral sex and foreplay since they do not involve the penetration of the penis into the vagina.
3. Clause 5 compels citizens of the republic to whistle blow on persons of the LGBTQI+ community. It is important to remember that before we are anything else religiously, biologically, ethnically, nationally, sexually_ we are human first. This clause sets citizens of Ghana up to plant seeds of hatred among themselves which could result in the shifting of the national stability we have enjoyed this far.
4. Clause 10 prohibits gross indecency subjecting persons engaged in this to a fine. The concept of gross indecency is relative and its unsettling to assume what might be considered decent according to one’s values will be the same for another. It is assuming all citizens of the republic must express themselves the same way.
5. Clause 12 to 16 infringes on the freedom of expression and media by banning the use of media, technological platforms, technological accounts, or any other means, produces, procures, markets, broadcast, disseminates, publishes or materials to promoting the LGBTQI+ community and subjects’ violators of this to no less than 5 years jail time.
6. Clause 15 infringes on the right to organize.
7. Clauses 19 to 23 anthropologically “others” members of the LGBTQI+ community by dehumanizing members of the community. Yet the cost of its proposed interventions of “love and care” are to be borne by the very members of the community while simultaneously wanting to prescribe jailtime?

The proposed bill apart from its gross dehumanization contradicts itself by providing half-baked argument to discriminate against law abiding citizens of the country on subjective paradigms. An example is seen with the bill’s encouragement of citizens of Ghana to report members or suspected members of the LGBTQI+ community to authorities while discouraging assault, abuse, or harassment whether verbal or physical. Verbal abuse, one of the more common forms of abuse, is a type of psychological abuse that involves the use of oral, gestured, and written language directed to a victim. Boltz M, Hoffman D (2017). Abuse is rarely predictable thus the ascribed “vulnerabilities” of members of the LGBTQI+ communities by this bill makes them easy targets for personal and institutionally backed banter and abuse rendering the LGBTQI+ truly unprotected.

Proposed Interventions:

The United Nations, an organization to which the Federal Republic of Ghana belongs agrees that the proposed bill is “are a textbook example of discrimination.” Therefore, below are some proposed interventions:

1. A vote against the bill rendering ineffective immediately
2. Access to inclusive proper sexual and reproductive health centers
3. Noninterference with the operations of the LGBT+ Ghana operations of its community center
4. Open dialogue between parliament, sexual and reproductive health professional and the LGBTQI+ community
5. Arrest and detention of persons who physically or verbally abuse and assault members of the LGBTQI+ community as that constitutes a hate crime
6. General respect for the constitutional rights and freedoms of members of the LGBTQI+ community as citizens of the Republic of Ghana

Conclusion:

Before we are anything else, we are human first. Dehumanizing members of the LGBTQI+ community in Ghana is no different than the dehumanizing of people of color during colonization through slavery and other inhumane circumstances. The “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill” proposed a system of discrimination which regresses the efforts our federal republic has attained since its independence from colonial rule. It is important that in the spirit of unity, we mobilize our full capacity and strength to push our motherland towards the progress we want to see. Every citizen counts. Every life matters. Every contribution, invaluable.